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CanVIG-UK review of ClinGen VHL Expert Panel Specifications to the ACMG/AMP Variant Interpretation Guidelines for VHL Version 1.1.0: Consensus to use relevant recommendations from the VHL Variant Curation Expert Panel (available at: <https://clinicalgenome.org/affiliation/50036/>, PDF attached below). Additional points of specification are given below where applicable.

Summary: Evidence towards Pathogenicity

Evidence element	Evidence strengths allowed				Thresholds/data-sources/applications specifically relevant to VHL
PVS1	VSTR	STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP
PS1		STR	MOD		As per VCEP, with the following addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For consideration of protein impact, please use the CanVIG-UK Consensus Specification weightings (strong, moderate)
PS2	VSTR	STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please use the International VHL Clinical Criteria¹ for phenotype scoring, see Appendix 1
PS3			MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buckley et al., 2024²: PS3_moderate (Function Score <-0.39)
PS4	VSTR	STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please use the International VHL Clinical Criteria¹ for case counting, see Appendices 1 and 2.
PM1			MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PM1_sup: ≥5 hotspots are required (instead of <10), aligning with other VCEP specifications.
PM2				SUP	As per VCEP
PM3					Not applicable, as per VCEP
PM4			MOD		As per VCEP
PM5			MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PM5_mod: Variant under examination has equal or larger Grantham Distance than reference variant PM5_sup: As above, but reference variant is classified as LP AND has only been reported in 1 individual
PM6		STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following change:

					Please use the International VHL Clinical Criteria ¹ for phenotype scoring, see Appendix 1
PP1		STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following change: Please use the International VHL Clinical Criteria ¹ for phenotype scoring, see Appendix 1
PP2					Not applicable, as per VCEP
PP3				SUP	As per VCEP
PP4					Not applicable, as per VCEP
PP5					Not applicable, as per VCEP

Summary: Evidence towards Benignity

BA1/BS1	Stand Alone	STR			As per VCEP
BS2		STR		SUP	As per VCEP
BS3		STR	MOD	SUP	As per VCEP, with the following addition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buckley et al., 2024²: BS3_strong (Function score >-0.23)
BS4		STR		SUP	As per VCEP
BP1					Not applicable, as per VCEP
BP2		STR		SUP	As per VCEP
BP3				SUP	As per VCEP
BP4				SUP	As per VCEP
BP5				SUP	As per VCEP
BP6					Not applicable, as per VCEP
BP7				SUP	As per VCEP

Appendices

Appendix 1: International criteria diagnostic guidelines

1	Multiple CNS or retinal hemangioblastomas (HB) or
2	CNS or retinal HB and one visceral lesion* or
3	+ve FH or a pathogenic variant in VHL gene & one CNS or retinal HB or visceral lesion*
*Clear-cell renal cell carcinoma, pheochromocytoma or paraganglioma, or pancreatic neuroendocrine tumour	

Appendix 2: Proband case-counting

Phenotype	Panel	Category	Points
International criteria	Not required	Highly specific	1
1 feature of VHL disease without FH	Done	Consistent	0.5
1 feature of VHL disease without FH	Not done	Non-specific	0.25
RCC&Pheo	Done	Consistent	0.5
RCC&Pheo	Not done	Non-specific	0.25
Non-specific criteria*	Done	Non-specific	0.25
Non-specific criteria*	Not done	Non-specific	0
Not available but published article in VHL cohort	May or may not have been done	Non-specific	0.25

*specific information on tumour types not provided

Panels – clear cell RCC – SDHB/C/D, Pheo – SDHB/C/D & RET = minimum genes tested

Version History/Amendments

Revised version	Date	Section	Update	Amended by	Approved by
1.0	22/05/2025	--	Initial Version	--	CStAG

References

1. Halperin, R., Arnon, L., Eden-Friedman, Y., & Tirosh, A. (2023). Unique Characteristics of Patients with Von Hippel-Lindau Disease Defined by Various Diagnostic Criteria. *Cancers*, **15**(6), 1657. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers15061657>
2. Maher, E., Neumann, H. & Richard, S. von Hippel–Lindau disease: A clinical and scientific review. *Eur J Hum Genet* **19**, 617–623 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ejhg.2010.175>.
3. Buckley, M., Terwagne, C., Ganner, A. *et al.* (2024). Saturation genome editing maps the functional spectrum of pathogenic *VHL* alleles. *Nat Genet* **56**, 1446–1455. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-024-01800-z>

ClinGen VHL Expert Panel Specifications to the ACMG/AMP Variant Interpretation Guidelines for VHL Version 1.1.0

Affiliation: VHL VCEP

Version : 1.1.0

Released : 1/10/2025

Release Notes :

Please see clarifications made to PM2, BA1 and BS1. We updated language to gnomAD v4, removed language around using the “non-cancer” set (which did not contain TCGA germline samples) as this set is no longer used in v4. We changed PM2_Supporting from complete absence in gnomAD to PM2_Supporting $\leq 1.56E-6$ GroupMax FAF. This is one order of magnitude less than the BS1 cut-off and strictly limits the presence of variants in gnomAD v4 but does not require complete absence.

V 1.1.0 Disease entity and transcript added

Rules for VHL

Gene: VHL (HGNC:12687) [↗](#)

Transcripts:
NM_000551.4

HGNC Name: von Hippel-Lindau tumor suppressor

Disease:
von Hippel-Lindau disease (MONDO:0008667) [↗](#) **Mode**

of Inheritance: Autosomal dominant inheritance

Criteria & Strength Specifications

PVS1

Original ACMG Summary

Null variant (nonsense, frameshift, canonical ± 1 or 2 splice sites, initiation codon, single or multi-exon deletion) in a gene where loss of function (LOF) is a known mechanism of disease.

Caveats:

- Beware of genes where LOF is not a known disease mechanism (e.g. GFAP, MYH7).
- Use caution interpreting LOF variants at the extreme 3' end of a gene.
- Use caution with splice variants that are predicted to lead to exon skipping but leave the remainder of the protein intact.
- Use caution in the presence of multiple transcripts.

Very Strong

LINK TO PVS1 DECISION TREE DOCUMENT:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mGfChgxbGVbzYn6Ggmb9rYvoGGah25II/view?>

Do not apply PVS1 for truncations that occur prior to Codon 54 (including frameshift events that start and end prior to Codon 54 but the truncation extends beyond Codon 54.)

Note1: Exon presence in biologically relevant transcripts: In some transcripts exon 2 of *VHL* is skipped and expressed at low levels. The function of this transcript is not fully known. Exon 2 comprises almost the entirety of the nuclear export function region of the Beta domain and is critical for known VHL function. Exon 1 contains the only initiator codons in *VHL*. Exon 3 contains the elongin binding function. ***All exons should be considered as "present in biologically relevant transcripts" in the PVS1 decision tree.***

Note 2: The 10% PVS1 downgrade to Moderate cannot apply to VHL because of the small size.

Nonsense Mediated Decay^{5 4} NMD experimental evidence in 1st exon after codon 54 and to 5' region of 2nd exon (codon 138).**

Critical Domains:

1st Beta (β) domain (63-154), especially Nuclear Export (114-155)

Alpha (α) domain (155-192), especially Elongin C binding (157 - 172)

Second Beta domain (193-204)

Truncating variants after Met54 and predicted to undergo NMD (from AA55-AA136/c.408) or in the beta or alpha domains can receive PVS1, and those outside the second Beta domain (205-213) can receive PVS1_Moderate downgrade to account for minimal loss of VHL protein. Notably a frame shift deletion at 205 is pathogenic in ClinVar (ID 18971) as are stop loss extension variants in the last codons (see PM4).

SPLICE: If any canonical exon is skipped, the variant receives PVS1. If a cryptic splice disrupts the reading frame, and is in a critical domain (AA63-AA204) or is predicted to undergo NMD (AA55-AA136) it receives PVS1. If it is outside a critical domain and predicted to undergo NMD (AA55-62), it receives PVS1_Strong (the second site outside of critical domains AA205-213 is not predicted to undergo NMD). If a cryptic splice does not alter the reading frame, and is in a critical domain (AA 63-204), it can receive PVS1_Strong, and if it is outside the critical domain (AA 205-213) or in an NMD prediction (AA 55-62), it receives PVS1_Moderate. Note: There is a cryptic exon (E1) in intron 1^{7 6}, and silent variants in exon 2 that are reported to cause skipping of exon 1. If there is functional evidence of exon skipping (RNA splice assay) then PVS1 can apply. Do not double count evidence. Ex. PVS1 should be used in place of PS3 functional evidence confirming splice alteration, but PS3 evidence code could still apply to other relevant assays confirming effect on HIF1/2a presence etc.

EXON DELETION: SVI PVS1 decision tree modified for whole exon deletions. There are only 3 exons in *VHL* and each has an important functional domain. Any exon deletion of *VHL* receives PVS1.

EXON DUPLICATION: Follow PVS1 decision tree. Note: few pathogenic exon duplications are reported in ClinVar. (ID:417571, ID:584137). These have no literature cited.

INITIATION CODON: VHL Met 1 (in VHL p30) truncation or missense would not affect VHL p19, as VHL has a second start at codon 54 (VHL p19), it cannot be scored in the PVS1 decision tree. After that, no other viable alternative starts are known. Start loss at codon 54 would presumably result in an impact, as VHL p30 and p19 would be truncated prior to any known functional domains (PVS1). Ong 2007 has 1 family (2 subjects) with Met54X and reports cerebellar hemangioblastomas. There is no functional study in the paper for this variant. Olschwang et al 1998 VHL Type 2A, one subject with 161insT (FS result). There is no functional study in the paper. Missense at Met 54 (VHL p19 initiation codon) would presumably not result in as strong an impact as the full length VHL p30 would still be produced (PVS1 decision tree = N/A). ClinVar has M54T (ID:819688) and M54L (ID:843990). M54T is uncertain, with no other evidence provided. M54L references M54I which segregates in homozygous state with erythrocytosis in individuals of Moroccan descent ^{9 8}, and those heterozygous for M54I did not present VHL phenotype ⁹.

Modification Disease-specific, General recommendation

Type:

PS1

Original ACMG

Summary

Same amino acid change as a previously established pathogenic variant regardless of nucleotide change.

Example: Val->Leu caused by either G>C or G>T in the same codon.

Caveat: Beware of changes that impact splicing rather than at the amino acid/protein level.

Strong

Applied only to variants with interpretation by the VHL VCEP or by a variant with pathogenicity established using VHL VCEP specifications.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

PS2

Original ACMG

Summary

De novo (both maternity and paternity confirmed) in a patient with the disease and no family history.

Note: Confirmation of paternity only is insufficient. Egg donation, surrogate motherhood, errors in embryo transfer, etc. can contribute to non-maternity.

Very Strong

A single proband cannot be very strong evidence, but multiple probands can be combined to reach very strong (4+ points).

Modification Strength

Type:

Strong

Phenotype highly specific for the gene (Danish Criteria) (≥ 2 but less than 4 *de novo* points).

Modification Strength

Type:

Moderate

Phenotype consistent but not highly specific. Ex. VHL spectrum cancer without family history or strong indication of VHL phenotype. (≥ 1 but less than 2 *de novo* points)

Modification General recommendation, Strength

Type:

Supporting

Phenotype consistent but not highly specific (≥ 0.5 but less than 1 *de novo* points) Ex. subject included in a VHL cohort, but specific information on tumor types is not provided.

Modification Strength

Type:

Instructions: Use the SVI-recommended scoring system (0.5 supporting, 1 moderate, 2 strong, 4 very strong) with disease-specific phenotype detailed as follows: Danish Criteria (see recently updated Danish Criteria ¹⁸), Consistent Phenotype (1 phenotype of VHL disease without family history or strong indication of VHL phenotype) or Nonspecific Phenotype (specific information on tumor types is not provided). Negative panel testing is required as follows: For Renal Cell Carcinoma, tumor histopathologies should be clear cell and a negative panel should include at least SDHB/C/D and for Pheochromocytoma only negative panels should include at least SDHB/C/D and RET. If paper states Danish or International Criteria but does not provide case-specific details, count these cases as "Phenotype consistent." If there is no family history of VHL disease, Renal Cell Carcinoma and Pheochromocytoma only will count as "Phenotype consistent" (with negative panel testing).

PS3

Original ACMG Summary

Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies supportive of a damaging effect on the gene or gene product.

Note: Functional studies that have been validated and shown to be reproducible and robust in a clinical diagnostic laboratory setting are considered the most well-established.

Supporting

Acceptable assays that display functional effect in VHL are the following:

- HIF 1/2a degradation assays -- HIF1/2a is not degraded and/or
- VBC complex stability is affected and/or
- Pathogenicity supported by abnormal ECM formation and impaired fibronectin binding ^{1, 2, 3, 17}

Multiple studies and publications confirm the role of VHL in HIF1/2a regulation and VBC complex stability for VHL Type 1, and 2A/B, as well as fibronectin binding/deposition and assays evaluating extra-cellular matrix composition. In-vitro assays should display total loss of HIF1/2a degradation (i.e. HIF1/2a presence) for VHL Type 1, and 2A/B. VHL Type 2C should display presence of HIF1/2a (with VBC complex stability variably affected and fibronectin deposition/extra cellular matrix composition affected). These assays are typically performed in Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC) cells lacking VHL, introducing normal pVHL as a control in addition to a variant-VHL, then comparing HIF1/2a levels to WT pVHL. Brnich et al proposed 10 controls to achieve PS3_Supporting and 11 for PS3_Moderate ¹⁰. We propose to *follow the workflow outlined in Brnich et al.* Type 2C VHL variants are typically missense variants in the alpha domain of VHL, and do not usually affect HIF1/2a. If HIF1/2a maintains presence and VHL Type 2C is suspected, assays evaluating fibronectin deposition or extracellular matrix assembly should be used.

SPlicing: PS3: RNA transcripts carrying splicing mutation display splicing defects in patient cells. **PS3_Moderate:** RNA transcripts carrying splicing mutation display splicing defects in in-vivo or in-vitro assays. **Functional Assay Documentation**

: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1w8P8zs1fHUolaAYmBL1jw-vcjsX3N_yh/view?usp=sharing

Modification Disease-specific, Strength

Type:

PS4

Original ACMG

Summary

The prevalence of the variant in affected individuals is significantly increased compared to the prevalence in controls.

Note 1: Relative risk (RR) or odds ratio (OR), as obtained from case-control studies, is >5.0 and the confidence interval around the estimate of RR or OR does not include 1.0.

See manuscript for detailed guidance.

Note 2: In instances of very rare variants where case-control studies may not reach statistical significance, the prior observation of the variant in multiple unrelated patients

with the same phenotype, and its absence in controls, may be used as moderate level of evidence.

Very Strong

16+ points the PS4 cut-off and Proband Scoring Tables from a mix of any of the following phenotypes: specific, consistent and nonspecific.

Modification Disease-specific,Strength
Type:

Strong

5-15 points the PS4 cut-off and Proband Scoring Tables from a mix of any of the following phenotypes: specific, consistent and nonspecific.

Modification Disease-specific,Strength
Type:

Moderate

2 - 4 points the PS4 cut-off and Proband Scoring Tables from a mix of any of the following phenotypes: specific, consistent and nonspecific.

Modification Disease-specific,Strength
Type:

Supporting

1 point the PS4 cut-off and Proband Scoring Tables from a mix of any of the following phenotypes: specific, consistent and nonspecific.

Modification Disease-specific,Strength
Type:

Instructions: See phenotype and points tables. When the phenotype meets Danish Criteria (panel is not required, unless only RCC+Pheo. If a case with RCC+Pheo does not have a panel, they are scored as "Nonspecific" (0.25 points)), count 1 point per proband. When the phenotype is consistent with VHL but is not highly specific (such as RCC+Pheo) count 0.5 and when not specific and no panel, count as 0.25. Unrelated probands are to be used, and may be aggregated across all three categories (highly specific Danish Criteria, Consistent and Nonspecific). If there is a pedigree with a choice of probands with VHL disease, choose the proband that most closely matches Danish Criteria. When the phenotype is not available (e.g. from a published article on a VHL cohort that does not detail the phenotype), count 0.25 points per proband. For example, for variant A, 2 probands meet Danish Criteria, 2 probands display Pheochromocytoma only and 4 probands were defined as VHL probands in a published manuscript but lack any further specific criteria or phenotypic details. This would be calculated as (2, 1 pt each per Danish Criteria proband) + (1, 0.5

pt each per Consistent proband) + (1, 0.25 pt each per Nonspecific proband) = 4. PS4 would be downgraded to moderate (PS4_Moderate).

PM1

Original ACMG Summary

Located in a mutational hot spot and/or critical and well-established functional domain (e.g. active site of an enzyme) without benign variation.

Moderate

Putative missense variants that are known germline hotspots AND/OR in key functional domains AND/OR somatic variants that have ≥ 10 instances for the same AA in cancerhotspots.org. See the table of Germline and Somatic Hotspots.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Supporting

Putative missense variants seen in somatic databases, having < 10 instances for the same AA in cancerhotspots.org. See the table of Germline and Somatic Hotspots.

Modification Strength

Type:

Instructions: *See germline and somatic hotspot residue table.* PM1 can be used for (1) known germline mutational hotspots, and for (2) currently 11 somatic hotspots (cancerhotspots.org) where there is not already a germline mutational hotspot (see Walsh et al 2018 ¹¹ and cancerhotspots.org(v2) ¹²): Following PM1 somatic hotspot recommendations through the ClinGen Germline/Somatic Subcommittee where: AA with ≥ 10 somatic occurrences in the same AA can receive PM1, while AA with < 10 can receive PM1_Supporting. It can also be used for (3) location in a key functional domain if a residue is not a germline or somatic hotspot.

PM2

Original ACMG Summary

Absent from controls (or at extremely low frequency if recessive) in Exome Sequencing Project, 1000 Genomes or Exome Aggregation Consortium.

Caveat: Population data for indels may be poorly called by next generation sequencing.

Supporting

PM2_Supporting can be applied for variants either absent from gnomAD or with ≤ 0.00000156 (0.000156%) GroupMax Filtering Allele Frequency in gnomAD (based on gnomAD v4 release). If no GroupMax Filtering Allele Frequency is calculated (ex. due to a single variant present), PM2_Supporting may also be applied.

Modification Disease-specific, Strength
Type:

Instructions: Follow all [SVI general guidance](#) on applying population filters.

PM3

Original ACMG Summary

For recessive disorders, detected in trans with a pathogenic variant
Note: This requires testing of parents (or offspring) to determine phase.

Not Applicable

Comments: Autosomal dominant.

PM4

Original ACMG Summary

Protein length changes due to in-frame deletions/insertions in a non-repeat region or stop-loss variants.

Moderate

In-frame insertion / deletions in the B and alpha domains and stop-loss variants adding significant additional amino acids to VHL ¹⁵ cites multiple pathogenic cases and experimental evidence of stop loss extensions in VHL that are associated with Type 2A VHL disease). The functional domains are: Beta (β) domain (AA 63 - 155, Nuclear Export), Alpha (α) domain (AA 156-192, Elongin C binding), and Second Beta (β) domain (AA 193-204).

PM4 does not apply to in-frame indels prior to codon 54 that do not alter the Met54 VHL p19 codon and beyond.

Modification Disease-specific
Type:

PM5

Original ACMG Summary

Novel missense change at an amino acid residue where a different missense change

determined to be pathogenic has been seen before.

Example: Arg156His is pathogenic; now you observe Arg156Cys.

Caveat: Beware of changes that impact splicing rather than at the amino acid/protein level.

Moderate

Pathogenicity of prior variant is established by interpretation of the VHL VCEP or variants with pathogenicity established using VHL VCEP specifications. The Grantham distance should be used to compare variants. The variant under consideration must be equal or a larger distance than the classified pathogenic variant (Grantham, 1974, Table 2¹⁶). Splice metapredictors should be used to ensure the variant is not predicted to have an effect on splicing.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

PM6

Original ACMG

Summary

Assumed *de novo*, but without confirmation of paternity and maternity.

Moderate

See PS2 evidence code for scoring and phenotypes. Assumed *de novo* receives half the points as compared to maternity and paternity confirmed *de novo*. If paternity and maternity are not confirmed, score as the PM6 code. PM6 can receive “VeryStrong” strength. For example, if there are >4 *de novo* probands with Danish Criteria and none have paternity confirmed, this can receive PM6_VeryStrong. Note: the VCI as of Nov 2022 does not allow PM6_VeryStrong. Instead apply the PS2 evidence code and increase the strength to “VeryStrong” with a note that paternity and/or maternity is not confirmed.

Modification Disease-specific, General recommendation

Type:

Instructions: See PS2 evidence code for scoring and phenotypes.

PP1

Original ACMG

Summary

Co-segregation with disease in multiple affected family members in a gene definitively known to cause the disease.

Note: May be used as stronger evidence with increasing segregation data.

Strong

>7 meioses across ≥ 2 families

Modification Strength

Type:

Moderate

5 - 6 meioses across ≥ 1 family.

Modification Strength

Type:

Supporting

3 - 4 meioses across ≥ 1 family.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Instructions: Meioses can be counted additively across multiple families. This code may only be applied when the phenotype is highly consistent with VHL (Danish Criteria in a family with history of disease).

PP2

Original ACMG Summary

Missense variant in a gene that has a low rate of benign missense variation and where missense variants are a common mechanism of disease.

Not Applicable

Comments: Do not use. While there are known pathogenic missense in VHL, there is also evidence of benign or common missense in VHL. gnomAD shows VHL is not intolerant to missense (Z score = -0.39). Missense variants in VHL will need to achieve pathogenic interpretation via other evidence codes.

PP3

Original ACMG Summary

Multiple lines of computational evidence support a deleterious effect on the gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc.).

Caveat: As many in silico algorithms use the same or very similar input for their predictions, each algorithm should not be counted as an independent criterion. PP3 can be used only once in any evaluation of a variant.

Supporting

For missense variants, use REVEL score ≥ 0.664 .

For splice variants, concordance of Splice AI (>0.5) and VarSeak (class 4 or class 5).

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Instructions: The Splice AI score alone can be applied if VarSeak is unable to accept the variant type. Note: for canonical splice variants do not use PP3 if PVS1 is applied.

PP4

Original ACMG

Summary

Patient's phenotype or family history is highly specific for a disease with a single genetic etiology.

Not Applicable

Comments: Combine with PS4 to avoid double counting probands.

PP5

Original ACMG

Summary

Reputable source recently reports variant as pathogenic, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to perform an independent evaluation.

Not Applicable

This criterion is not for use as recommended by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation VCEP Review Committee. [PubMed : 29543229](#)

BA1

Original ACMG

Summary

Allele frequency is above 5% in Exome Sequencing Project, 1000 Genomes or Exome Aggregation Consortium.

Stand Alone

Use a BA1 cut off of ≥ 0.000156 (0.0156%) GroupMax Filtering Allele Frequency in gnomAD (based on gnomAD v4 release).

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Instructions: Follow all [SVI general guidance](#) on applying population filters.

BS1

Original ACMG

Summary

Allele frequency is greater than expected for disorder.

Strong

Use BS1 cut off of ≥ 0.0000156 (0.00156%) GroupMax Filtering Allele Frequency in gnomAD (based on gnomAD v4).

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Instructions: Follow all [SVI general guidance](#) on applying population filters.

BS2

Original ACMG

Summary

Observed in a healthy adult individual for a recessive (homozygous), dominant (heterozygous), or X-linked (hemizygous) disorder, with full penetrance expected at an early age.

Strong

VHL is not highly penetrant *at an early age*. BS2 can be applied if: There are at least 3 individuals, all ≥ 65 yo, unaffected, harboring the same variant, ***with full phenotyping and screening*** for the absence of VHL-related cancers.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Supporting

VHL is not highly penetrant *at an early age*. BS2_Supporting can be applied if: At least 3 individuals, all ≥ 65 yo, unaffected, harboring the same variant, ***lacking full phenotyping and screening***, with no noted VHL-related cancers

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

BS3

Original ACMG

Summary

Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies show no damaging effect on protein function or splicing.

Supporting

- HIF 1/2a assay replicates WT function and/or
- VBC complex stability is not affected and/or
- ECM formation/fibronectin binding is unaffected

This rule can be used and weighted as appropriate for functional tests of variants prior to codon 54 (which show the VHL19 product is not impacted). Evidence of benign effect for VHL Type 1 and 2A/B can be seen when HIF1/2a displays degradation (i.e. replicates WT function), and/or the VHL Elongin C, Elongin B, Cullin2 RBX1 (VCB-CR) E3 ubiquitin ligase complex stability is not affected and/or ECM formation/fibronectin binding is unaffected. Note: VHL Type 2C variants typically do not affect HIF1/2a; absence of HIF1/2a alone when testing a suspected VHL Type 2C variant should not be used for BS3. Functional studies of fibronectin and ECM formation are needed for VHL Type 2C. Follow modified SVI guidance for functional assays, general controls and benign controls. For splicing variants (and intronic/synonymous), RNA assays must demonstrate no impact on splicing.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

BS4

Original ACMG

Summary

Lack of segregation in affected members of a family.

Caveat: The presence of phenocopies for common phenotypes (i.e. cancer, epilepsy) can mimic lack of segregation among affected individuals. Also, families may have more than one pathogenic variant contributing to an autosomal dominant disorder, further confounding an apparent lack of segregation.

Strong

Lack of segregation is seen in affected members of ≥ 2 families

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Supporting

Lack of segregation is seen in 1 family.

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Instructions: For BS4, affected members of the pedigree should fulfill the Danish Criteria for VHL. BS4 should not be used if the affected members are only affected with pheochromocytoma (e.g. VHL 2c) and/or Renal Cell Carcinoma. Family members should also be fully characterized for VHL

manifestations to be considered unaffected, and be at least 65 years old (age at which full penetrance should be reached).

For example: two siblings who both have VHL as per the Danish criteria, one has a *VHL* variant, and the other sibling does not, BS4 could be used.

Conversely, two siblings both fully characterized, one sibling has VHL manifestations, the other sibling is >65 yo and does not have VHL manifestations. If both siblings carry the *VHL* variant, BS4 could be used.

If the above are fulfilled, BS4 strong could be used if lack of segregation of the variant is seen in affected members of two or more families and BS4_supporting be used if one family is observed.

If a parent fulfills the Danish criteria for VHL disease, but the child is phenotyped and has no manifestations, BS4 cannot be used as the child could develop VHL manifestations at a later age.

BP1

Original ACMG Summary

Missense variant in a gene for which primarily truncating variants are known to cause disease.

Not Applicable

Comments: This rule code does not apply to this gene, as truncating variants account for only a portion of disease-causing variants.

BP2

Original ACMG Summary

Observed in trans with a pathogenic variant for a fully penetrant dominant gene/disorder or observed in cis with a pathogenic variant in any inheritance pattern.

Strong

- i) -variant observed in trans with a known pathogenic variant (phase confirmed), in the absence of congenital polycythemia (clinical manifestations or molecular)
- ii) -OR observed in the homozygous state in an individual without personal &/or family history of Von Hippel-Lindau disease or congenital polycythemia
- iii) -OR observed *in cis* or with unknown phase with three or more different pathogenic *VHL* variants

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Supporting

-variant is observed *in cis* (or phase is unknown) w/ a pathogenic *VHL* variant

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Instructions: BP2 should not be used in the presence of any clinical or molecular findings of congenital polycythemia

BP3

Original ACMG

Summary

In frame-deletions/insertions in a repetitive region without a known function.

Supporting

BP3 can be applied to the 8x GXEEX AA repeat motif in the 5' end of *VHL* p30 (AA14-AA48). Otherwise, the rest of the coding regions in *VHL* do not contain repeats (and none contain LINE/SINE, low complexity or other repeat types as identified by RepeatMasker) and BP3 is not applicable.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

BP4

Original ACMG

Summary

Multiple lines of computational evidence suggest no impact on gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc)

Caveat: As many *in silico* algorithms use the same or very similar input for their predictions, each algorithm cannot be counted as an independent criterion. BP4 can be used only once in any evaluation of a variant.

Supporting

Due to the lack of benign variants, and the drop in classification accuracy for benign *VHL* variants, missense predictors should not be used to assign the BP4 evidence code.

BP4 can be applied to assess lack of splicing impact, with concordance of Splice AI (≤ 0.1) and VarSeak (Class 1 or Class 2).

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

Instructions: The Splice AI score alone can be applied if VarSeak is unable to accept the variant type.

BP5

Original ACMG Summary

Variant found in a case with an alternate molecular basis for disease.

Supporting

BP5 can be applied for two or more co-occurrences with pathogenic variants in a different gene that fully explained the patient's phenotype, but specific circumstances would need to be met in order for a case to be considered for inclusion. First, the variant in the other gene must be considered highly penetrant, with both the individual's age, tumour type and gender taken into consideration. Additionally, the patient's personal and family history (including up to 2nd degree relatives) should not overlap with features seen in VHL and VHL tumour histologies. As an example, an individual with a personal and family history of pheochromocytoma who harbored a *VHL* variant in addition to a pathogenic *SDHB* variant BP5 would not apply, because pheochromocytoma is a known risk in VHL and the *VHL* variant might have contributed to this individual's pheochromocytoma cancer risk. However, an individual with a personal and family history of chromophobic RCC who was positive for a *VHL* variant as well as a pathogenic *FLCN* variant would be considered for BP5 application, as non-clear cell RCC is not associated with VHL disease.

Modification Disease-specific

Type:

BP6

Original ACMG Summary

Reputable source recently reports variant as benign, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to perform an independent evaluation.

Not Applicable

This criterion is not for use as recommended by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation VCEP Review Committee. [PubMed : 29543229](#)

BP7

Original ACMG Summary

A synonymous variant for which splicing prediction algorithms predict no impact to the splice consensus sequence nor the creation of a new splice site AND the nucleotide is not highly conserved.

Supporting

To evaluate splice prediction, use the BP4 code. If BP4 is met for lack of splice effect, BP7

can be applied to silent or intronic variants where the PhyloP score is ≤ 0.2 .

Modification General recommendation

Type:

Rules for Combining Criteria

Pathogenic

1 Very Strong (*PVS1, PS2_Very Strong, PS4_Very Strong*) **AND** \geq **1 Strong** (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*)

1 Very Strong (*PVS1, PS2_Very Strong, PS4_Very Strong*) **AND** \geq **2 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

1 Very Strong (*PVS1, PS2_Very Strong, PS4_Very Strong*) **AND 1 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*) **AND 1 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

1 Very Strong (*PVS1, PS2_Very Strong, PS4_Very Strong*) **AND** \geq **2 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

\geq **2 Strong** (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND** \geq **3 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND 2 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*) **AND** \geq **2 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND 1 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*) **AND** \geq **4 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

Likely Pathogenic

1 Very Strong (*PVS1, PS2_Very Strong, PS4_Very Strong*) **AND 1 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND 1 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND** \geq **2 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

\geq **3 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

2 Moderate (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*) **AND** \geq **2 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

1 Moderate (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*) **AND** \geq **4 Supporting** (*PS2_Supporting, PS3_Supporting, PS4_Supporting, PM1_Supporting, PM2_Supporting, PP1, PP3*)

1 Strong (*PS1, PS2, PS4, PP1_Strong*) **AND 2 Moderate** (*PS2_Moderate, PS4_Moderate, PM1, PM4, PM5, PM6, PP1_Moderate*)

Benign

\geq **2 Strong** (*BS1, BS2, BS4, BP2_Strong*)

1 Stand Alone (*BA1*)

Likely Benign

1 Strong (*BS1, BS2, BS4, BP2_Strong*) **AND 1 Supporting** (*BS2_Supporting, BS3_Supporting, BS4_Supporting, BP2, BP3, BP4, BP5, BP7*)

Files & Images

Functional Assay Documentation:

VHL PVS1 Decision Tree:

PS4 Cut-Offs:

Evidence Code Strength	VHL VCEP Proband Point Cut-Offs
Very Strong (PS4_VeryStrong)	16+
Strong (PS4)	5-15
Moderate (PS4_Moderate)	2-4
Supporting (PS4_Supporting)	1

Denovo-Confirmed-and-Not-Confirmed:

Phenotypic consistency	Points per Proband	
	Confirmed de novo	Assumed de novo
Phenotype highly specific for gene (Danish criteria)	2	1
Phenotype consistent with gene but not highly specific e.g. VHL 2c, Pheo Only, gene panel -ve	1	0.5
Phenotype consistent with gene but not highly specific and high genetic heterogeneity* Pheo only, VHL tested only	0.5	0.25
Phenotype not consistent with gene	0	0

*Maximum allowable value of 1 may contribute to overall score

Meiosis:

Evidence Strength	VHL VCEP Meiosis Counts
Strong (PP1_Strong)	>7 <u>meioses</u> across >=2 families
Moderate (PP1_Moderate)	5-6 <u>meioses</u> across >=1 families
Supporting (PP1)	3-4 <u>meioses</u> across >= 1 families

Proband Scoring:

Proband Scoring (unrelated probands):

Danish Criteria	1 point
Consistent but not highly Specific Phenotype (ex. <u>Pheochromocytoma</u> only, VHL 2C, Panel testing negative.)	0.5 points
Nonspecific, Unspecified Probands	0.25 points

Germline and Somatic Hotspots :

Hotspots	Germline or Somatic	References
R167, C162, L178, Y98, N78, P86	Germline	Stebbins et al (PMID:10205047)
65,76,78,80,86,88,96,98,112,117,161,162,167,170,176	Germline	Chiorean et al 2022 (PMID: 35475554)
S65, S68, V74, N78, S80, P86, W88, L89, S111, Y112, G114, H115, W117, D121, L135, I151, L158, R161, C162, L169	Somatic (germline hotspots marked through, use as "germline" not somatic)	cancerhotspots.org & Walsh et al 2018 (PMIDs: 29247016 and 30311369)

References

- Ohh M Yauch RL et al. *The von Hippel-Lindau tumor suppressor protein is required for proper assembly of an extracellular fibronectin matrix.* **Mol Cell** (1998) 1 (7) p. 959-68. 10.1016/s1097-2765(00)80096-9 9651579 [↗](#)
- Clifford SC Cockman ME et al. *Contrasting effects on HIF-1alpha regulation by disease-causing pVHL mutations correlate with patterns of tumourigenesis in von Hippel-Lindau disease.* **Hum Mol Genet** (2001) 10 (10) p. 1029-38. 10.1093/hmg/10.10.1029 11331613 [↗](#)
- Kamada M Suzuki K et al. *von Hippel-Lindau protein promotes the assembly of actin and vinculin and inhibits cell motility.* **Cancer Res** (2001) 61 (10) p. 4184-9. 11358843 [↗](#)
- Micale L Muscarella LA et al. *VHL frameshift mutation as target of nonsense-mediated mRNA decay in Drosophila melanogaster and human HEK293 cell line.* **J Biomed Biotechnol** (2009) 2009 p. 860761. 10.1155/2009/860761 20145706 [↗](#)

5. Taylor C Craven RA et al. *Determination of the consequences of VHL mutations on VHL transcripts in renal cell carcinoma.* **Int J Oncol** (2012) 41 (4) p. 1229-40. 10.3892/ijo.2012.1561 22825683 [↗](#)
6. Lenglet M Robriquet F et al. *Identification of a new VHL exon and complex splicing alterations in familial erythrocytosis or von Hippel-Lindau disease.* **Blood** (2018) 132 (5) p. 469-483. 10.1182/blood-2018-03-838235 29891534 [↗](#)
7. Buffet A Calsina B et al. *Germline mutations in the new E1' cryptic exon of the VHL gene in patients with tumours of von Hippel-Lindau disease spectrum or with paraganglioma.* **J Med Genet** (2020) 57 (11) p. 752-759. 10.1136/jmedgenet-2019-106519 31996412 [↗](#)
8. Caravita S Deboeck G et al. *Pulmonary arterial hypertension associated with a von Hippel-Lindau gene mutation.* **J Heart Lung Transplant** (2016) 35 (9) p. 1138-9. 10.1016/j.healun.2016.07.002 27578599 [↗](#)
9. Bartels M van der Zalm MM et al. *Novel Homozygous Mutation of the Internal Translation Initiation Start Site of VHL is Exclusively Associated with Erythrocytosis: Indications for Distinct Functional Roles of von Hippel-Lindau Tumor Suppressor Isoforms.* **Hum Mutat** (2015) 36 (11) p. 1039-42. 10.1002/humu.22846 26224408 [↗](#)
10. Brnich SE Abou Tayoun AN et al. *Recommendations for application of the functional evidence PS3/BS3 criterion using the ACMG/AMP sequence variant interpretation framework.* **Genome Med** (2019) 12 (1) p. 3. 10.1186/s13073-019-0690-2 31892348 [↗](#)
11. Walsh MF Ritter DI et al. *Integrating somatic variant data and biomarkers for germline variant classification in cancer predisposition genes.* **Hum Mutat** (2018) 39 (11) p. 1542-1552. 10.1002/humu.23640 30311369 [↗](#)
12. Chang MT Bhattarai TS et al. *Accelerating Discovery of Functional Mutant Alleles in Cancer.* **Cancer Discov** (2018) 8 (2) p. 174-183. 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-17-0321 29247016 [↗](#)
13. Hwang S Ku CR et al. *Germline mutation of Glu70Lys is highly frequent in Korean patients with von Hippel-Lindau (VHL) disease.* **J Hum Genet** (2014) 59 (9) p. 488-93. 10.1038/jhg.2014.61 25078357 [↗](#)
14. Hong B Ma K et al. *Frequent Mutations of VHL Gene and the Clinical Phenotypes in the Largest Chinese Cohort With Von Hippel-Lindau Disease.* **Front Genet** (2019) 10 p. 867. 10.3389/fgene.2019.00867 31620170 [↗](#)
15. Sorrell AD Lee S et al. *Clinical and functional properties of novel VHL mutation (X214L) consistent with Type 2A phenotype and low risk of renal cell carcinoma.* **Clin Genet** (2011) 79 (6) p. 539-45. 10.1111/j.1399-0004.2010.01464.x 20560986 [↗](#)
16. Grantham R *Amino acid difference formula to help explain protein evolution.* **Science** (1974) 185 (4154) p. 862-4. 10.1126/science.185.4154.862 4843792 [↗](#)
17. Bluysen HA Lolkema MP et al. *Fibronectin is a hypoxia-independent target of the tumor suppressor VHL.* **FEBS Lett** (2004) 556 (1-3) p. 137-42. 10.1016/s0014-5793(03)01392-9 14706840 [↗](#)
18. Louise M Binderup M Smerdel M et al. *von Hippel-Lindau disease: Updated guideline for diagnosis and surveillance.* **Eur J Med Genet** (2022) 65 (8) p. 104538. 10.1016/j.ejmg.2022.104538 35709961 [↗](#)